

Effect of Cyclic Hygrothermal Aging on the Interlaminar Shear Strength of Carbon Fiber/Bismaleimide (BMI) Composite

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1. Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites are widely used as primary structural components in aerospace industry due to their attractive properties such as high strength-to-weight ratio and excellent corrosion resistance. Bismaleimides (BMI) resins are always used in high temperature application due to their superior thermal stability and fatigue resistance at high humidity [1]. These composite components are generally exposed to harsh environments with changing temperature and humidity in service, which accelerate decline in the composites' physical and mechanical properties strongly [2,3]. Thus understanding the effect of moisture absorption-desorption on composites is essential to improve component durability.

Water absorption induces a severe degradation on the composites' mechanical properties. Various possible mechanisms were reported to explain the effects of moisture on composites: matrix plasticization, matrix swelling, micro-cracks propagation, hydrolysis, degradation of interface, interfacial debonding etc [4-8]. Plasticization is supposed to be a reversible phenomenon [4] while Interfacial debonding decreases mechanical properties irreversibly [6,7]. Besides, chemical ageing affects the molecular structure inducing chain scissions and thus causes embrittlement permanently [5]. Reverse damage can be eliminated after drying by removal of water [4]. Many researchers studied the influence of wet-dry cycles on composites [9-12] for better understanding the effect of real work conditions on composites. S.Roy [21] found that water uptake and loss during wet-dry cycles can cause stresses and micro-cracks. The cyclic process was described as auto-accelerative by Tsenoglou [10] because the damage accumulates in subsequent wet-dry cycles, leading to even greater depths of penetration of water. Newman [12] showed that water resistance of flax-epoxy composites was significantly different over multiple cycles from that after single cycle.

Hygrothermal aging decreases mechanical

performance of composites by damaging matrix and interface [22-26]. Different approaches have been investigated to study interfacial mechanical properties: macromechanical tests such as short beam test; and micromechanical tests [13] such as the single fiber pull-out, single fiber fragmentation test, microindentation test and microdroplet test. Short beam test is widely used for measuring the macroscopic interlaminar shear strength of composites (ILSS) due to its convenience [27,28]. In this paper, ILSS evolution of CF/BMI composites subjected to various aging process was studied systematically for a better understanding of cyclic hygrothermal aging mechanisms. Four kinds of BMI matrix i.e. 5405, 5428, QY8911 and QY9511 resin were used in the composites. ILSS evolution of 5405 matrix composites reinforced by T300 and CCF300 were compared. The effects of cyclic hygrothermal aging, test temperature, and hygrothermal history on ILSS of CF/BMI composites were investigated respectively.

2 Experimental Method

2.1 Materials

Various kinds of composites were studied in this paper: T300/5405, CCF300/5405, CCF300/5428, CCF300/QY8911 and CCF300/QY9511. The matrix resin were commercial BMI resin: BMI resin 5405 and 5428 produced by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials; BMI resin QY8911 and QY9511 provided by Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute. Two kinds of carbon fiber were incorporated in BMI 5405: T300 supplied by Toray Co. and CCF300 provided by Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd. All unidirectional composite panels were manufactured by autoclave molding according to curing process specified by resin manufacturers. The fiber volume fraction (V_f) of all the composite samples was $65 \pm 2\%$.

2.2 Interlaminar Shear Strength Test

The short beam shear samples of $20 \times 6 \times 2 \text{mm}^3$ were performed on Instron 5500 testing machine according

to the ASTM D-2344 at 25°C and 150°C respectively. The mean value of shear strength for least 5 specimens was calculated.

2.3 Aging test in hygrothermal environment

Absorption experiment: Dry specimens were put into a humidity chamber and immersed in distilled water at 71°C.

Desorption experiment: After moisture absorption for a certain hours, specimens were removed from water and dried in a desiccator at 85°C until the weight reached constant.

Wet-dry cycle: Cycling process with 2 different periods (7 days and 14 days) was tested. The process of wetting specimens for 7 days in 71°C distilled water and then drying at 85°C for 83h to a constant weight is called one cycle with period of 7 days. By analogy, one cycle with period of 14 days means wetting specimens for 14 days in 71°C distilled water and then drying at 85°C for 94h to a constant weight. The same procedure was followed for the second and third cycle, as shown in Fig. 1. The sample state is described by “a_n”, where “a” and “b” mean cyclic period and cycling times respectively.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Effect of absorption and desorption on ILSS of CF/ BMI

ILSS of T300/ 5405, CCF300/ 5405, CCF300/5428, CCF300/QY8911 and CCF300/QY9511 tested at 25°C after immersing for different days are plotted in Fig. 2. They are compared with the corresponding ILSS of the initial dry state, represented by a white bar on the left of each “bundle” of bars. The same behavior is observed, the ILSS of samples decreases as a function of time initially and roughly stabilizes after immersion for 14 days, which reveals that equilibrium damage level is reached after an aging time of 14 days. Although ILSS is always used to determine the interfacial strength, it is actually a comprehensive reflection of interfacial performance and matrix properties [14,28]. Hence ILSS decline on wet condition is not only due to interfacial debonding [6,7] and interfacial degradation but also a result of physical i.e. matrix plasticization [4] and chemical i.e. hydrolysis [5], modification of the polymer matrix. It can be observed that the composites with 5405 matrix reinforced by CCF300 have a lower retention rate in ILSS during hygrothermal aging (respectively 90.4%, 82.4% and 86.5% after immersing for 7,14,42 days) compared to that reinforced by T300 (respectively 95.7%, 89.6% and 93.6% after immersing for 7,14,42

days). This indicates that interface of T300/5405 is superior to that of CCF300/5405 in heat and humidity resistance. Desorption after immersing for 7 days makes the ILSS higher than its original state for all composites except CCF300/QY9511. We have also noticed that a small residual weight gain remained in the material after drying which is also observed by L.R.Bao [9]. Maybe the abnormal increase is related to toughening effect of the residual water molecules. In terms of CCF300/QY9511, it is worth noting that its ILSS evolution during hygrothermal aging differs notably from the behavior of other composites where a sharp decrease can be observed

In order to illustrate the reversibility of damage caused by moisture absorption, desorption experiments have been carried out. As expected, ILSS can be recovered after drying, which is also presented in Fig. 2 as dense shade, with values corresponding to the vertical axis. It is evident that upon drying at 85°C, the original ILSS can be regained for T300/5405, CCF300/5428 and CCF300/QY8911, whereas ILSS of CCF300/5405 and CCF300/QY9511 cannot be recovered thoroughly. It indicates that reversible damage and permanent damage coexist to degrade the ILSS of wet samples. It has been generally established that plasticization is a reversible phenomenon [4] while chemical aging and interfacial debonding irreversibly affect mechanical behaviour of composites [5-7]. It is also believed that interface is the determining factor of the reinforcement mechanisms, especially under wet conditions. Thus it can be concluded that interface of CCF300/5405 and CCF300/QY9511 is damaged during hygrothermal aging which is consistent with the observation by Sun Pei et al [18,19]. In Fig. 2, it is particularly interesting that desorption can only shift ILSS of CCF300/QY9511 back to 77.7% of its original state after immersion for 7 days. It indicates that the weak interface offers an easy path for water molecules to penetrate and thus degrade the interface which can also explain the slump of ILSS after immersion for 7 days. Besides, comparison between ILSS evolution of T300/5405 and CCF300/5405 also confirms the viewpoint mentioned above that interface of T300/5405 is superior to that of CCF300/5405 in heat and humidity resistance.

3.2 Effect of test temperature on ILSS of CF/BMI

Composites used in the aerospace industry are always loaded at high temperature, thus it is of practical necessity to investigate the effect of test temperature on ILSS. Evolution curves of ILSS tested at 25°C and 150°C during hygrothermal aging are fitted using Phani-Bose model (see Eq.(1)). Phani-Bose model^[16]

which mainly considers the effect of matrix plasticization describes ILSS evolution as a function of immersion time and test temperature.

$$\sigma(t) = (\sigma_0 - \sigma_\infty) \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) + \sigma_\infty \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma(t)$, σ_0 and σ_∞ are, respectively, the composite interlaminar shear strength at times t , initially and after an infinite time and τ is a characteristic time dependent on temperature. The smaller τ indicates the more decline on mechanical properties of composites. Fitted curves and experimental data are obtained in Fig.3 and estimated parameters are reported in Table 1. From Fig. 3, it is evident that fitted curves at 150°C have a better correlation with experimental data than that at 25°C. This is because higher temperature facilitates plasticization in hygrothermal environment. Besides, τ is smaller at 150°C implying that temperature and humidity work coefficiently to accelerate the decline of ILSS. Values of estimated parameter σ_∞ are similar to ILSS values for the composites aging for 14 days whether at 25°C or 150°C, which is an indication of saturated damage after immersing for 14 days. The dramatically high τ of composite CCF300/5428 might be due to its fluctuation in ILSS after immersing for 7 days which makes it deviate from Phani-Bose model.

3.3 Effect of wet-dry cycles on ILSS of CF/BMI

The ILSS values during the wet-dry cycles for each composite are presented in Fig. 4. It is readily observed that at 25°C ILSS shows a progressive decline during the 2nd cycle, but it is steady during the 3rd cycle when cyclic period is 7 days. While ILSS after each cycle is similar when cyclic period is 14 days. The desorption step does not reverse the modifications caused by sorbed moisture, such as microcracks and interfacial debonding, which makes it more accessible for moisture in the re-absorption steps. When samples are immersed in water for 7 days, damage in the composites is unsaturated so that acceleration of moisture absorption could cause a progression of damage during the subsequent re-absorption. After the 2nd cycle, damage has reached saturation, thus little decline can be caused in ILSS in the 3rd cycle. Similarly, saturated damage induced by wetting for 14 days in the 1st cycle makes it hard to induce more decline in ILSS in the subsequent cycles.

When tested at 150°C, the similar behavior can also be observed during the cycles with 7 days as one period, while different phenomenon occurs when cyclic period is 14 days. This phenomenon is that 14₂ specimens have a lower ILSS than 14₁ specimens. It can be concluded that wet-dry cycle has an

unnoticeable effect on the damage saturation level, which can only appear at high temperature. Furthermore, removal of moisture causes a larger recovery of ILSS compared to that tested at 25°C, while almost none of them can recover to initial dry state after 3 times cycling. This phenomenon implies that high temperature degrades ILSS of composites by facilitating plastication and accelerating permanent damage such as extension of debonding and cracks at the same time.

As can be seen, ILSS of composites cycled with 2 times for 7 days is always higher than that of composites immersing for 14 days consecutively whether at 25°C or 150°C. It can be instructive in practical application.

3.4 Effect of hygrothermal history on ILSS of CF/BMI

Results depicting ILSS of 5 kinds of CF/BMI composites after various hygrothermal treatment tested at 25°C are shown in Fig. 5. “A+B+C” represents process of hygrothermal treatment, where A and B mean cycling days successively, the last alphabet C means immersing days before testing. For example, the mean of “7+7+14” is as follows: immerse specimens in distilled water at 71°C for 7 days and dry in a desiccator at 85°C until the weight reaches constant. Then immerse the dried specimens in distilled water at 71°C for 7 days and dry in a desiccator at 85°C again. Immerse the specimens in distilled water at 71°C for 14 days at last.

From Fig. 5, it is evident that after immersing for 7 days, ILSS of composites with hygrothermal history is always lower, while after wetting for 14 days, they're nearly the same. It means that damage caused by hygrothermal history has an effect on declining ILSS of composites with unsaturated damage, but its effect is hard to appear on specimens with saturated damage. This phenomenon, in fact, further supports the conception of damage saturation and the effects of damage accumulation which is discussed in the previous sections. It can be observed that ILSS₇₊₁₄ of all the CF/BMI composites is slightly lower than ILSS₁₄₊₇. Aging process of “14+7” and “7+14” both induce saturated permanent damage to composites, hence the phenomenon can only be explained by the more serious matrix plasticization of the latter one. From the above, it can be concluded that reversible damage is affected by the last immersing time dominantly and permanent damage is affected by the total immersion time as a result of damage accumulation effect.

4. Conclusion

(1) During hygrothermal aging, ILSS of CF/BMI composites decreases with immersion-time increasing overall until plateau is nearly reached after immersion for 14 days. After desorption, ILSS can be recovered to various degrees by reversing some damage. Effects of desorption on ILSS of CF/BMI can reflect their interfacial characteristics during hygrothermal aging indirectly. Interface of T300/5405 is better than that of CCF300/5405 in heat and humidity resistance. Interface of CCF300/QY9511 is damaged the most seriously by hygrothermal aging among all the composites studied in this paper (T300/5405, CCF300/5405, CCF300/5428, CCF300/QY8911, CCF300/QY9511).

(2) Test temperature has a great effect on ILSS. Under high test temperature, hygrothermal aging declines the ILSS of composites sharply by facilitating plastication and accelerating permanent damage such

as extension of debonding and cracks at the same time. Phani-Bose model which considers the effect of matrix plasticization mainly is more reasonable to fit ILSS evolution of composites at high test temperature.

(3) Conception of damage saturation and effect of damage accumulation are confirmed in this paper. When damage of composites is unsaturated, ILSS of composites decreases in subsequent wet-dry cycles by damage accumulation until damage saturation is reached. Once damage of composites is saturated, it is hard to induce progressive damage and decline ILSS in re-absorption in our experimental materials.

(4) Wet-dry cycle has an effect on the level of damage saturation, but it's so unnoticeable that it can only appear at high test temperature. Irreversible damage is history-dependent so that it is affected by the total immersion time, while reversible damage such as matrix plasticization is mainly impacted by the last immersion time.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of hygrothermal cycling process

Fig. 2. ILSS of CF/BMI composites tested at 25°C during hygrothermal aging (white bars represent the ILSS of initial dry composites; bars of various sparse shade represent the ILSS of composites after immersion for certain days; bars of various dense shade represent the corresponding ILSS recovery of wet specimens after subsequent desorption)

Fig. 3. ILSS evolution curves of composites tested at 25°C and 150°C

Table. 1. Estimated parameters of Phani-Bose model

T	τ		σ_{∞} (MPa)		σ_{14} (MPa)	
	25°C	150°C	25°C	150°C	25°C	150°C
T300 /5405	5.8	3.9	89.9	36.8	87.7	35.3
CCF300 /5405	4.9	4.0	83.1	34.6	80.8	34.0
CCF300 /5428	31.2	5.2	80.7	42.1	87.9	44.4
CCF300 /QY8911	8.4	3.9	88.3	43.4	86.5	43.6
CCF300 /QY9511	5.4	5.3	75.3	37.1	78.5	40

Fig. 4. ILSS of CF/BMI composites tested at 25°C and 150°C during the cyclic process of wetting and drying

Fig. 5. ILSS of CF/BMI composites after various hydrothermal history tested at 25 °C

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